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Perception-Based Analysis of Local Investors' Response to CPEC Development in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigate the investment behavior of local investors with respect to the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) in Pakistan-Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP). The study targeted three segments of beneficiaries, namely Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Chamber of Commerce, the employees of the Peshawar Railway Track, and Peshawar social science experts. Convenience sampling technique was used considering the exhaustive nature of working out on the entire population. A sample of 308 respondents was chosen out of 2114 individuals to be involved in in-depth interviews as per the population-sample size determination rules by Sekaran (2003). The primary data were gathered by the use of a structured questionnaire that was aimed at measuring all the required variables. In the analysis of the data, univariate and bivariate methods of statistics were used. The paper give the vision of local investors on the perception and responses towards CPEC-led investment opportunities and its help in understanding how the region is participating in significant economic development initiatives.

Keywords: CPEC, Local Investors, Investment, Industrial Product Unit, Special Economic Zones

Introduction

Pakistan aims at the robust regional connectivity by 2025, and the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) is significant in connecting the nation towards the regional and international markets. It is a project that is a linkage between Pakistan and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), South Asian Association of Regional Cooperation (SAARC) and Central Asia Regional Economic Cooperation (CAREC). CPEC is one of the components of the One Belt, One Road (OBOR) program in China to increase the level of trade integration, regional connectivity, and mutual economic development. The concept of Pak-China Community of Shared Destiny was initially coined by the Chinese President, Xi Jinping, to his Pakistani counterpart, Mamnoon Hussain, by stating that both countries needed to work together and prosper. Chinese analysts consider CPEC the support of this vision (Aarish, 2013). In May 2013, the historic CPEC accord was signed to link the Gwadar Port in Pakistan to the Western China of Kashgar. Later visits at high levels also cemented this partnership: Chinese premier Li Keqiang visited Pakistan in May 2013, Prime Minister Nawaz Sharif visited China in July 2013 and president Mamnoon Hussain visited China in February 2014 where more than 250 agreements had been signed in different fields, including trade, energy, infrastructure and socio-economic cooperation. This was a milestone as China and Pakistan settled on the Early Harvest Projects of the Kashgar Gwadar Economic Corridor (KGEC) that included the Karakoram Highway upgrading, Karachi Lahore Motorway construction, construction of the new Gwadar International Airport and Special Economic Zones (SEZs) (Daraz et al., 2018). In November 2014, fourteen more agreements were signed to fasten the implementation of CPEC during the visit of Prime Minister Nawaz Sharif to China (The News, 2014). Later, the Chinese President and Pakistan signed Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) of \$46 billion deeming CPEC as one of the biggest bilateral economic projects in the area (Business Management Authority, 2015). CPEC has the objective of transforming Pakistan infrastructure through creation of roads, railways, ports, energy development and optical fiber networks. The investments planned are mostly about energy (74%), transport infrastructure (13%), and mining of coal (20%), and most importantly affordable energy production (Business Management Authority,

2015). The trade route between south western China and Africa as well as the Middle East and Europe has been reduced by CPEC which benefits both the countries mutually and also opens more markets to China. In addition to economic growth, CPEC will contribute to social growth through the generation of jobs, the enhancement of access to education and healthcare and the elevation of the standard of living in Pakistan (UN, 1995). Enhancement of the transport infrastructure in addition to easing trade and lowering the cost of transactions also enhances foreign direct investment (FDI) by increasing accessibility and lowering the cost of operation (Wheeler, 1992; Elizondo, 2015). Research has shown that an improvement in infrastructure by 10 percent in terms of transport infrastructure can result in an 8 percent growth in industry output (Suh, 2003). Industrialization, investment, and regional integration will also get a further push through the development of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) in Gilgit-Baltistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Punjab, and Balochistan (Daraz et al., 2025). These SEZs will not only draw in the domestic and international investors but also result in the sustainable economic development and the better socio-economic conditions (Shah, 2014). CPEC will also enhance technological advancement, development of human capital and industrial diversification (Buckley, 2002). Traditionally, China and Pakistan have a deep strategic relationship based on their shared geopolitical interests, in particular, the common antagonism towards India (Parveen, 2015; Jehanzeb, 2015). The Karakoram Highway (KKH) was constructed between 1978 and 1996 that formed the basis of land connectivity between China and the Gulf region. The Gwadar Port will help in the reduction of the 12,000-mile distance of trade between China and the Middle East creating a direct point of access to the market of Africa, Middle East, and European markets via Pakistan. This partnership emphasizes the unwavering aid China provided to Pakistan in terms of infrastructure and technological advancement and proves the years-old connection between the two countries (Parveen, 2015; Jehanzeb, 2015). Essentially, the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor is not just an infrastructure project, but a vision of a regional integration, economic growth and prosperity through shared grounds. It is likely to transform the economic environment in Pakistan by increasing connectivity, investment inflows, employment and sustainable development in a wide range of regions (Khan et al., 2023).

Materials and Methods

The paper is a perception paper, which will examine the investment behavior of the local investors with reference to the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP). The sampled data sets were in three essential beneficiary areas of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Chamber of Commerce, Peshawar Railway Track employees, and social science experts located in Peshawar, KP. The statistical tools were appropriately chosen and used to make accurate and reliable conclusions about the relationship between dependent and independent variables (Rahman, 2018). A convenience sampling technique was used since sampling the whole population was impossible. Out of 2,114 people, 308 people were chosen in the sample of in-depth interviews based on the sample size determination guidelines suggested by Sekaran (2003). The structured questionnaire was used to gather primary data to uncover different variables of the study. The questionnaire was in three major sections: Background information of respondents, Perceived effects of the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (dependent variable), and the investment behavior of local investors (independent variable). The responses were assessed in terms of the three point Likert scale. The questionnaire was pre-tested on validity and reliability before the actual data collection was performed (Hakim, 2018). To analyze the data, two

tools of analysis were used: univariate and bivariate. The summary of the data was done with the percentage and frequency distribution under univariate analysis, and bivariate analysis through the Chi-square test to compare the relationship between the variables.

Results and Discussion

This part will entail two forms of analysis namely, univariate and bivariate. The univariate analysis defines and identifies the data derived by presentation in frequencies and percentages in the form of a table. On the other hand, the bivariate analysis uses the inferential statistics (Chi-square test) to test the association between the dependent variable which is China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) and the local investor's investment.

Frequency Distribution and Proportion of Local Investors Investment

S.No	Attributes	S.A	A	N	D.A	S.D.A	Total
1	CPEC is the establishment of special economic zones	129(41.9)	178(57.8)	1(0.3)			308(100)
2	Special economic zones will attract the local investors for investment	98(31.8)	209(67.9)	1(0.3)			308(100)
3	Installation of industrial product unit through CPEC will induce the local investors for investment	56(18.2)	151(49)	101(32.8)			308(100)
4	Development of transport infrastructures in CPEC project attract internal investors for investment	248(80.5)	58(18.8)	2(0.6)			308(100)
5	Decrease distance of transport route and reduce cost of communication through CPEC also attract the local investors for investment	245(79.5)	63(29.5)				308(100)
6	People will invest in local industries of goods due to good infrastructure	118(38.3)	186(60.4)	4(1.3)			308(100)

7	Reduction in transport price due to improved transport infrastructure through CPEC also attract local investors to invest in local goods like cotton, wheat, sports goods and garments to mobilize these goods into international market	68(22.1)	240(77.9)				308(100)
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Figure in the table show frequencies, figure in parenthesis show percentage. **(S.A)** denote strongly agree, **(A)** denotes agree, **(N)** denotes neutral, **(D.A)** denotes Disagree and **(S.D.A)** denotes strongly disagree.

The results of the above table indicate the perceptions of respondents on the effects of the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) on the local investment in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP). The findings indicate that a large percentage of the sampled respondents identify the formation of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) as a part and parcel of the CPEC model. Amongst 308 participants, 129 (41.9) people strongly agreed and 178 (57.8) people agreed that CPEC consists of SEZs, with only 1 respondent (0.3) people holding a neutral position. It shows that there is a lot of knowledge and acceptance of SEZs as a critical aspect of CPEC initiative. In the same manner, the introduction of SEZs was viewed as one of the significant factors in lure local investors. Out of the respondents 98 (31.8%) were highly in agreement with the claim that SEZs would stimulate local investment and 209 (67.9) agreed with it though only 1 respondent (0.3) was indifferent. The results provide indication that most of the local stakeholders consider SEZs as an engine of economic activity and industrial development in the province. On the issue of industrial production units that constitute yet another major constituent of CPEC, 56 respondents (18.2) strongly agreed and 151 (49) agreed that the installation of industrial units would be an attraction to investors, and 101 respondents (32.8) were neutral. Despite the general positive answer, the percentage of the neutral answers was rather high, which indicates that not all the respondents were sure about the practical application and advantages of these industrial efforts. The statistics also suggest that the development of transport infrastructure within the framework of CPEC is viewed as one of the major sources of local investment. Within the number of their total respondents 248 (80.5) strongly agreed and 58 (18.8) agreed that better internal transport networks will improve accessibility and trade and local investment. The number of respondents who were neutral was 2 (0.6). This consensus is overwhelming, which stresses the extreme attention transport infrastructure should receive in enhancing business confidence and economic growth in the region. Another point stressed by the respondents was that the CPEC implementation would result in shortening of the trade routes and communication costs, which would, in turn, increase local investments. To be more specific, 245 (79.5) strongly agreed and 63 (20.5) agreed with this opinion. The high agreement is a result of the belief that the low cost of operation and better logistics can greatly make local businesses better as far as the investment climate is concerned. In addition, the respondents reported good attitudes towards the quality and affordability of local products produced in the framework of industrialization as an activity by CPEC. Out of the respondents 118 (38.3) strongly responded that better

quality and affordability would encourage investors to invest in the local industries and 186 (60.4) respondents gave the affirmative response but 4 respondents (1.3) remained neutral. It implies that competitiveness of the product and cost-effectiveness has been considered as a major driver to local investment. Finally, in relation to the question of the effect of lowered transport expenses provided by better CPEC infrastructure, 68 respondents (22.1) strongly agreed and 240 (77.9) agreed that developments would enhance investment in domestic goods (e.g., wheat, cotton, sport goods and garments) as well as their entry into global markets. This collective opinion leads to a common view on the fact that CPEC will increase the potential of exports and economic integration both nationally and regionally. On the whole, the results indicate that the perceptions of the respondents are very positive regarding whether CPEC will spur local investment in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Most people consider CPEC as a complex development program that will improve infrastructure, industrialization, efficiency in trade and availability of the market. The high rates of consensus of the variables throughout show a great deal of optimism in the implications of CPEC in promoting economic growth, employment creation, and competitiveness of the region. Nevertheless, the low percent of neutral answers concerning industrial units implies that the policy needs to be better defined and the process of practical implementation of such projects should be communicated to ensure that investors are not scared.

Association between CPEC and Investment through Local Investors

The project of CPEC involves provision of all the requisite ingredients of development. They are the installation of industrial products zones, development of existing roads, as well as the induction of new ones. In addition, to this project, another gigantic objective is a unabated and unhindered transportation of goods, between China and Gawadar. This project would provide the optimum inclusion of the whole socially and economically selective segment by way of employment and business prospects.

Association between CPEC and Investment through Local Investors

S.No	Attributes	Local Investors			Total	Statistics
		Investment	S.A	A		
1	CPEC will be establish Special Economic zones (SEZ)	S.A	64(20.8)	65(21.1)		$\chi^2=31.36$ P=(0.000)
		A	57(18.5)	121(39.3)		
		N	1(0.3)			
		Total			308(100)	
2	Special Economic Zones (SEZ) will attract the local investors for investment	S.A	35(11.4)	63(20.5)		$\chi^2=87.85$ P=(0.000)
		A	87(28.2)	122(39.6)		
		N			1(0.3)	
		Total	122(39.6)	186(60.4)		
3	The installation of industrial product units will induce the investors for investment	S.A	83(26.9)	165(53.6)		$\chi^2=57.84$ P=(0.000)
		A	39(12.7)	19(6.2)		
		N	2(0.6)			
		Total	122(39.6)	186(60.4)		
4	People will invest in local goods of industries	S.A	8(2.6)	110(35.7)		
		A	114(37)	72(23.4)		

	due to good infrastructure	N					$\chi^2=72.37$ $P=(0.000)$
		Total	122(39.6)	186(60.4)		308(100)	
5	The development of transport infrastructure will attract the investors for investment	S.A	83(26.9)	165(53.6)		248(80.5)	$\chi^2=81.25$ $P=(0.000)$
		A	39(12.7)	19(6.2)		58(18.8)	
		N			2(0.6)	2(0.6)	
		Total	122(39.6)	186(60.4)		308(100)	
6	The decrease in distance route and reduction in communication cost will attract the investors to invest locally	S.A	83(26.9)	162(52.6)		245(79.5)	$\chi^2=172.84$ $P=(0.000)$
		A	39(12.7)	24(7.8)		63(20.5)	
		N					
		Total	122(39.6)	186(60.4)		308(100)	
7	The reduction in transport cost will due to improved transport infrastructure through CPEC people will invest in local goods, like garments, wheat, wool and dry fruits and mobilize to international market	S.A	8(2.6)	60(19.5)		68(22.1)	$\chi^2=69.027$ $P=(0.000)$
		A	114(37)	126(40.9)		240(77.9)	
		N					
		Total	122(39.6)	186(60.4)		308(100)	

Figure in the table represent frequency and figure in parenthesis represent percentage. Symbol (S.A) represent strongly agree, (A) represent agree and (N) represent neutral. According to the obtained results in the table, the association between the China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) and the creation of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) is very significant ($P = 0.000$). This proves that the emergence of SEZs is a natural part of CPEC. The zones will serve the purpose of hosting key economic activities since they will bring different sectors of the society on board. The inferences are similar to the findings made by Shiekh (2014), who highlighted the fact that SEZs would be set up in various regions of countries, especially in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) and Balochistan and thus create social and economic prosperity in such regions (Ullah et al., 2024). These developments will aid in domestic and foreign investment, which will improve connectivity of the region and boosting economic growth in regions of strategic importance. The rejuvenation of the Pakistani economy, therefore, would also lead to prosperity in western parts of China. In line with this, the close and statistically significant relationship ($P = 0.000$) was observed between the creation of production units of industries by CPEC and the local investment increase. The other notable correlation ($P = 0.000$) was found between the progress in the infrastructure in the context of CPEC, and the increase in the investment in the local goods. Also, a close relationship ($P = 0.000$) has been observed between the development of transport networks and the local participation of investors. These results are in line with the findings made by Shiekh (2014) in the view that CPEC will result in shorter distances with improved transport infrastructure, lowering of communication costs, ease of installing industrial units, enhanced efficiency of deliveries, and decreased inventory costs. Similar observations made by Wheeler (1992) that the improvement in transportation infrastructure and social amenities are the catalysts of investments due to the minimization of operation impediments. Schwartz (1996) further divided the infrastructural impact into two categories, i.e. horizontal impact, lowering the cost of operations; and vertical impact, lowering the transport costs and enhancing

accessibility. The two effects are favourable to investment environment. The research also established a significantly strong null correlation ($P = 0.000$) between the minimized transport routes, lesser communication costs, and maximized local investment using CPEC. This finding is also congruent with Shiekh (2014), who stated that the reduction in the distance to travel and diminished communication costs stimulate domestic investment. Similarly, there was a notable correlation ($P = 0.000$) between infrastructure development and improved investor confidence which validated the infrastructural improvements as a magnet to both the local and foreign investors. The results highlight the fact that CPEC has enabled widespread involvement of the domestic investors, which has been largely affected by the establishment of an effective transport and communication infrastructure. Improved infrastructure guarantees ease of the transport of goods, minimization of distance, and minimization of costs- thus enhancing investment prospects. These findings resonate with the claim by Khan (1999) that the local products can become more competitive in the global market, increase self-sufficiency, and connect Pakistan with the global markets with the help of such projects as the Karakoram well-known Gwadar Economic Corridor (KGEC) (Daraz et al., 2021). He also pointed out that these corridors promote major economic activities along the transport corridors, thus providing employment and generating income in the different provinces. They will strengthen the exports of Pakistan including sports goods, garments, wheat, and cotton as they are set up along CPEC routes, and at the same time, they will help to empower the local economies. According to the obtained results in the table, the association between the China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) and the creation of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) is very significant ($P = 0.000$). This proves that the emergence of SEZs is a natural part of CPEC. The zones will serve the purpose of hosting key economic activities since they will bring different sectors of the society on board. The inferences are similar to the findings made by Shiekh (2014), who highlighted the fact that SEZs would be set up in various regions of countries, especially in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) and Balochistan and thus create social and economic prosperity in such regions. These developments will aid in domestic and foreign investment, which will improve connectivity of the region and boosting economic growth in regions of strategic importance. The rejuvenation of the Pakistani economy, therefore, would also lead to prosperity in western parts of China. In line with this, the close and statistically significant relationship ($P = 0.000$) was observed between the creation of production units of industries by CPEC and the local investment increase. The other notable correlation ($P = 0.000$) was found between the progress in the infrastructure in the context of CPEC, and the increase in the investment in the local goods. Also, a close relationship ($P = 0.000$) has been observed between the development of transport networks and the local participation of investors. These results are in line with the findings made by Shiekh (2014) in the view that CPEC will result in shorter distances with improved transport infrastructure, lowering of communication costs, ease of installing industrial units, enhanced efficiency of deliveries, and decreased inventory costs. Similar observations made by Wheeler (1992) that the improvement in transportation infrastructure and social amenities are the catalysts of investments due to the minimization of operation impediments. Schwartz (1996) further divided the infrastructural impact into two categories, i.e. horizontal impact, lowering the cost of operations; and vertical impact, lowering the transport costs and enhancing accessibility. The two effects are favourable to investment environment. The research also established a significantly strong null correlation ($P = 0.000$) between the minimized transport routes, lesser

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Conclusion

The research results indicate that the influence of China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) on the local investment and economic growth of the region in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is quite powerful. The results indicate that the CPEC initiatives, including the introduction of Special Economic Zones (SEZs), installation of industrial product units, and the development of transport and communication infrastructures, are strongly related to the rise in the involvement of local investors. The overall effect is that, these developments have made the opportunities of making investments more viable, as transportation and communication have been lowered, accessibility has been made easier, and a business environment favorable. The findings that support the presence of SEZs inspires domestic and foreign investments through the infrastructural enhancements and creation of a suitable environment through reduced operations costs and increased market availability are validated. Moreover, the establishment of CPEC and industrial zones enhance regional connectivity and provide employment opportunities. Generally, the findings of the research show that CPEC is an effective economic booster in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan and also a play pivotal in the global economy. The CPEC project also economically stabilize the region and promote inclusive participation and development.

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